

4onse: analysis of Four times Open Non-conventional system for Sensing the Environment

Tank Management Application Report

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Executive summary

This report presents the approach of developing tank management model for Deduru Oya basin of Sri Lanka. The selected tank to develop the model is Deduru Oya reservoir, which is the largest man made tank in the basin. The main objective of developing the tank management model is to test the reliability of 4ONSE data in hydrological modelling and application of those data in regional water resources management. The model has been developed for estimating the inflow to the reservoir from upper catchment area. Application of simulated results in deciding the opening height of the radial gates of the reservoir, has also demonstrated in the report.

1 Introduction

There are 103 natural river basins of Sri Lanka which cover 90% of the total land extent. The remaining 10% which is situated along the coast and Jaffna peninsula is covered by small watersheds which are not much important in hydrological aspect. From the entire land area, 2/3rd belongs to the dry zone which is characterized by significant number of manmade reservoirs called tanks. As a result of these significant hydrological features, riverine floods and the floods created by tanks are most commonly seen in Sri Lanka. In dry zone, tanks are the most important and effective storage facilities to retain flood water. Flood control in tanks can effectively mitigate flood disasters and store water for use in the lean seasons.

However, inclusion of hydrological modelling approaches for flood control in tanks is not practiced among water practioners of Sri Lanka due to many reasons such as, inadequacy of quality data, high purchasing cost of modelling software, lack of expertise knowledge in handling software, etc. The regional scale catchments are characterized typically by natural variability in climatic and land-surface features (Wooldridge, S.A. and Kalma, J.D., 2001). The existing hydro-meteorological network in Sri Lanka is strongly insufficient for adequately accounting for this climatic heterogeneity. Studies done on hydrological models have found the very strong influence of weather station density and their measurements on hydrological model outputs (Andréassian, et. al, 2001; Faurès, et. al, 1995; Duncan, et.al, 1993; Chaplot, et.al, 2005). Especially the rainfall, which is the major input for any hydrological model, can vary greatly with small distances. Hence, inadequate representation of rainfall distribution over a watershed may result in producing unreliable model outputs (Warusavitharana, et.al, 2018).

The existing hydro-meteorological network of Deduru Oya river basin consists only several stations. During the rainy periods, reservoir managers face difficulties in taking timely decision on deciding the magnitude of flood flows for the safe disposal of excess flow. Currently, the reservoir managers release water from the reservoir once it comes to a particular level. This creates floods in the downstream areas due to intolerable quantity of water received to the downstream. Therefore, the flood risk in the downstream areas can be reduced to a considerable level, if the reservoir mangers take prior judgments about the water quantity that should be released time to time, without waiting till the last moment to release the huge quantity of water. Hence, there is a strong need to reduce the flood risk in the area by estimating the inflow to the tanks with sufficient lead time, to protect human lives and reduce damages.

Thanks to the 4ONSE project, Deduru Oya basin now has dense weather station network which records the data at 10 minutes interval. Out of the 27 weather stations, 14 are located at upper basin. The upper basin area consists of four stream (Deduru Oya, Maguru Oya, Kimbulwana Oya and Hakwatuna Oya) which start from the central high lands and merged at the Deduru Oya reservoir. The stations of the upper sub-basin are deployed in a manner where the large sub-catchment (Deuduru Oya) has high number of stations while the small sub-catchment has (Maguru Oya) has low number of stations. The high-density arrangement enables to replace missing weather data in the hydrological model, using the data of the nearest weather station. Further, the tank management application presented in this report demonstrates the capability of 4ONSE weather stations' data in estimating the inflows to the tanks during the rainfall events. Soil and Water Assessment Tool (SWAT) has been used to develop the hydrological model. SWAT is a continuous time model, which limits the application of model for detailed level flood simulation. However, the sub-hourly simulation allows analyst to extract useful outputs on total water inflow at flood peaks and flood peak timing, which directly useful for real time flood management.

2 Application of IoT in tank management

Reservoir is an artificial or natural lake or pond which is used to collect and store water for multipurpose activities such as drinking water supply, irrigation, flood control, hydropower generation and recreation. In Sri Lanka, reservoirs are called as tanks. Management is defined by the Oxford dictionary as "the process of dealing with or controlling things or people". Hence the "tank management" can be defined as the "process of dealing with or controlling the operation of releasing water from tanks". Tank water release decision is one of the challenging task for reservoir operator in order to determine the quantities of water to be stored and to be released from a reservoir (Wurbs, 1993). During flood events, they need to release adequate water from the tanks, ensuring that the reservoir capacity is at a safe level and water to be released will not trigger a flood downstream. Naturally, tank water levels rise when rainfalls occurred upstream. The gate opening decisions to release the water is crucial to make most of the time due to the unavailability of a proper decision support system to estimate the inflow to the tanks with the aid of the realtime weather data at upper catchment. Hence, a late decision might cause overflow at the downstream areas and might affect the dam's structure. Since the advent of computers, many efforts have been taken to establish a decision support system for reservoir flood control (Robillard, et.al, 1979; Unver, et.al, 1987; Ford & Killen, 1995; Miller, et.al, 1996; Huang & Yang, 1999; Ford, 2001; Shim, et.al, 2002). However, application of these systems in developing countries is often not possible because of high costs and constraints pertaining to available technologies for data collection, transmission, modelling and forecasting.

Internet of Things (IoT) has been around for the past few years and is gaining recognition with the breakthrough of advanced wireless technology (Huang & Li, 2010; Ucklemann, et.al, 2011). The most important thing in IoT is it provides the necessary infrastructure to transparently access sensors, processes and actuators using standardized protocols regardless of hardware, operating systems or location" (Presser, et.al., 2009; Roggen, et al., 2013). The potentials offered by the IoT make it possible to develop numerous applications based on it.

The IoT based applications have been started to popular as a more cost-effective product, after the integration of open hardware and open software in system development. The open source software packages and open hardware sensors have become widely used on a global scale in reducing costs of environmental monitoring (Bitella, et.al, 2014; Formisano, et.al, 2015; Sadler, et.al, 2014; Samourkasidis & Athanasiadis, 2014; Prescott, et.al, 2016). The scientific community, especially in developing countries are limited by technical skills, modern computer hardware, and software availability. Proprietary software are typically expensive and may not work in old hardware. In this background, open source technologies enables broad and relatively inexpensive access to scientific workflows, which is especially important in developing countries (Camara & Fonseca, 2007). This has created room for water practitioners and researchers to use and apply modelling, assessment and analysis tools for effective management, monitoring and modelling of water resources. However, combination of open hardware, open software and open standards has been limited to only few cases (Sadler, et.al, 2014; Samourkasidis & Athanasiadis, 2014; Prescott, et.al, 2016; Hicks, et.al, 2011) focusing on recording real-time data on meteorological parameters, air quality, water quality. Therefore, application of combined open technologies in flood management in catchment areas, especially with regard to flood control in tanks still remains as an unexplored area.

3 Hydrological modelling

3.1 Hydrologic models, hydrologic cycle and water balance equation

The heart of any flow forecasting system is a hydrological model (Askew, 1989). A model is a simplified representation of a complex system. Thus, a hydrologic model is a simplified representations of a part/s of the hydrologic cycle - precipitation, evapotranspiration, infiltration, surface runoff, routing and interflow / sub-surface flow.

The quantitative measurements of the parts of the hydrological cycle can be expressed in the water balance equation as variables. The Water balance equation is a fundamental equation applied in the science of hydrology. The equation expresses the balance between the water input and water output. In simplest form, water balance can be expressed as:

$$\text{Water input} = \text{Water output} + \text{Change in storage} \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

Although the hydrologic models are termed in various names such as watershed models, hydro-meteorological models, runoff models, etc. depend on their application; the typical approach is to use meteorological observations or forecasts as input data to estimate the runoff. Runoff is variously referred to as stream flow or river flow, stream or river discharge, or catchment or watershed yield. This is normally expressed as a volume per unit of time (Ex: m^3/s).

There are different types of hydrological models, namely, theoretical models/ physically based models, empirical models, conceptual models, linear models, lumped models, distributed models, semi-distributed models, stochastic models, deterministic models, event based models, continuous process models, etc. Most of the time, hydrological models exist as combinations of several types of models such as lumped conceptual, physically based

distributed and conceptual distributed. The tank management model developed in this study belongs to physically based semi-distributed model category.

Physically based models are developed from principles of physics and the models are run either at micro scale or meso scale. Spatial heterogeneities of land use, soil and input variables are considered in these models. Calibration of most physically based hydrologic models is usually performed by the comparison of predicted and observed hydrograph. Physically based hydrologic models have different discretization schemes as grid based, irregular grid based and sub-basin scheme. In here, the discretization in hydrologic models refers to the process of dividing the basin area into discrete counter parts. The micro-scale physically based models can be considered as distributed models, in which the river basin is discretized as a grid mesh.

Although the distributed models are capable of modelling the runoff process in more detailed manner at pixel level, the models demand a massive amount of data. They need quality data, require greater simulation and calibration time and high error propagation. Conversely, in semi-distributed models, where river basin is discretized into limited number of sub-basins based on the topography, hydrological parameters such as meteorological variables, land use, soil and elevation are aggregated at sub-basin level. Therefore, they can avoid unnecessary data demand and computation burden for calibration. Hence semi-distributed models are more appropriate for regional scale areas where the data is less demanding.

Hydrological models can be further categorized as deterministic and stochastic based on the process of parameterization. In simple terms, a deterministic model can be defined as a model that takes a single-valued input and produces a single-valued output (Abbaspour, et.al, 2018). Most hydrologic time series may be thought of as stochastic processes since they contain both deterministic and stochastic components. In this application, the stochastic modelling approach was followed for parameterization of the model. The term "parameterization" is elaborated in the section 3.2 of this report.

3.2 Model calibration and uncertainty assessment

The term 'calibration' refers to a procedure where the difference between model simulation and observation are minimized (Abbaspour, et.al, 2018). The objective function can be optimized as per the equations given below:

$$\text{Min} : g(\theta) = \sum_{j=1}^v [w_j \sum_{i=1}^{n_j} (x_0 - x_s)_i^2] \text{ Equation 2}$$

$$\text{Min} : g(\theta) = \sum_{j=1}^v [w_j (1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n_j} (x_0 - x_s)_i^2}{\sum_{i=1}^{n_j} (x_0 - \bar{x}_0)_i^2})] \text{ Equation 3}$$

Where g is the objective function, θ is a vector of model parameters, x_0 is the observed variable, x_s is the corresponding simulated variable, v is the number of measured variables to be used to calibrate the model, w_j is the weight of the j^{th} variable.

The results of calibration and validation are the best indicators to decide the model performance. Model calibration is the process of adjusting selected input parameter values

and initial conditions to obtain simulated values that match measured observations with the desired accuracy (Zeckoski, et al., 2015). However, due to spatial variability in the processes, many of the physical models are highly complex and generally characterized by a multitude of parameters (Xuan, et.al, 2009). Since, the input parameter which governs the hydrological processes vary with the geographical setting and the climatic condition of the basin / sub-basin, naturally the parameter values have high degree of uncertainty.

Lindenschmidt, et.al (2007) have identified model structure, input data and parameters as the main factors which influence for uncertainty in hydrological modeling. Renard, et. Al (2010) have identified four main sources for hydrologic modelling uncertainties. They are:

(1) Uncertainties of the conceptual model

Abbaspour (2008) have identified four issues for model uncertainties. They are:

- a. Uncertainties which arise as a result of simplifications of the conceptual model – when the hydrological model becomes more simplified, it ignores some most important hydrological processes.
- b. Uncertainties due to ignoring some most important hydrological processes in the model, which occur in the watershed.
- c. Sometimes all the processes are included in the model, but uncertainties may arise when their occurrences in the watershed are unknown to the modeler
- d. Uncertainties may also create when some important hydrological processes are ignored and when their occurrences in the watershed are unknown to the modeler.

(2) Uncertainties in input data

The typical approach of any hydrological model is to use meteorological observations or forecasts as input data to estimate the runoff and the storage. Sampling and measurement errors in meteorological observations are mainly caused for predictive uncertainties in runoff. However, type of input data required for modeling depends on the hydrological modeling software. Rainfall is the prime and the most sensitive input data applied in any hydrological model. Since its rate of variation across an area is comparatively higher than other meteorological observations, inadequate representation of rainfall distribution over a watershed, may result in producing unreliable model outputs.

Further, errors associated with other ancillary data such as DEM, land use and soil layers can also be contributed for producing inaccurate results.

(3) Uncertainty in parameterization

Parameter is a quantifiable characteristics of a feature or process represented in a model (Malone, et al., 2005). Parameterization is the process of assigning values to model parameters (Zeckoski, et al., 2015).

Since spatial areas have different proportions and types of land use and soil types under different land forms and climatic conditions, parameters usually have substantial spatial variability. Hence, correct parameterization is an important step in model calibration and must be based on the knowledge of the hydrologic processes and variability in soil, land use, slope, and location as defined by the sub-basin number (Arnold, et al., 2012). Parameterization, therefore, could be defined as “the process of imparting the analyst’s knowledge of the physical processes of the watershed to the model” (Arnold, et al., 2012). Inability to assign correct

values to model parameters and disregarding the parameters which mostly influence on the hydrological processes result in increasing the predictive uncertainty of hydrological models. SWAT's watershed area is divided into number of HRUs based on land use, soil and slope. Hence, during the process of parameterization, estimating large number of parameters associated with each HRU is a cumbersome task.

Most often, the values of the parameters are determined through previous studies done for the watershed area. In the absence pre-determined parameter values, the direct measurement of parameters in the watershed is expensive, time consuming and more difficult. Hence most of the time, these parameters are typically not measured directly, instead, they are often indirectly estimated via model calibration, where the modelled values are fitted to observations (Zhang, et.al, 2014).

(4) Output uncertainty

During the model calibration, the accuracy of the model output – runoff, is compared with the discharge of the stream at specific locations – river gauges. Measurements of the water level are continually recorded at the river gauge either manually or automatically. A stage-discharge relationship equation is needed to convert this water level into a volume (or “discharge”). This equation is developed by measuring the flow of the river (discharge) at different water levels (stages). As pointed out by Schmidt (2002), uncertainties in the stage-discharge relationship are emerged as a result of (1) natural uncertainties – changes in the river cross sections (2) knowledge uncertainties – incomplete understanding of the true physical processes (3) data uncertainties – human-induced observation and data processing errors. Hence, in order to apply hydrological models in the practical water resource investigations, careful calibration and uncertainty analysis are required (Beven & Binley, 1992; Vrugt, et.al, 2003; Yang, et.al, 2008).

4 Case study area

The selected tank to develop the model is Deduru Oya reservoir, which is the largest tank in the Deduru Oya river basin which has a capacity of 75,000,000m³. The reservoir receives water from four streams from the upper catchment – Maguru Oya, Deduru Oya, Kimbulwana Oya and Hakwatuna Oya (Figure 1). The reservoir is located at the center of the basin and the aforementioned four streams are merged at the reservoir. Hence it is a major determinant of controlling the floods in the lower basin.

Figure 1: Stream network and major tanks of Deduru Oya basin

During the rainy periods, reservoir managers face difficulties in taking timely decision on deciding the magnitude of flood flows for the safe disposal of excess flow. Currently, they release water from the reservoir once it comes to a particular level. This creates floods in the downstream areas due to the intolerable quantity of water received to the downstream. Therefore, the flood risk in the downstream areas can be reduced to a considerable level, if the reservoir managers take prior judgments about the water quantity that should be released time to time, without waiting until the last moment to release the huge quantity of water. Hence, there is a strong need to reduce the flood risk in the area by means of establishing a suitable decision support system to estimate the stream flow.

However, such a decision support system has not been established yet for the tanks in Deduru Oya basin and not even for any other tank / reservoir in Sri Lanka, owing to the below constraints:

- The hydro-meteorological network coverage is restricted to certain locations of the country due to higher installation and maintenance costs. Therefore, the existing coverage / density of the stations are inadequate to simulate the hydrological processes at sub-basin level.

- The communication network of the automated stations belong to Meteorological Department are malfunctioned at present. Therefore, obtaining continuous real time data for modelling purposes becomes an issue.
- Use of hydrological modelling for decision making is not widely practiced among decision makers of Sri Lanka due to the lack of knowledge, high purchasing cost of modelling software and lack of data on model parameters.

5 Hydrological modelling tool

5.1 Selection of modelling tool

Three most popular open source tools on hydrological modelling have been studied and compared to find the most appropriate one to develop the tank management model. WEAP, SWAT and HEC-HMS are the three tools which used for the comparison. Accordingly, SWAT (Soil and Water Assessment Tool) tool was selected for this study and the reasons for selecting the tool are given below:

- It is an existing, readily available and well documented water resources modelling tool.
- Since SWAT is a physically based semi-distributed model, the physical processes associated with water movement is directly modeled by SWAT using the input data of weather, soil properties, topography, vegetation, and land use.
- Hence, the model is able to calculate most of its parameter values based on the above input data uploaded into the model.
- Its Graphical User Interface (GUI), is embedded in the popular and widely used GIS environments – ArcGIS (ArcSWAT), QGIS (QSWAT) and MapWindow (MWSWAT). In this study, the model was developed using QSWAT plugin embedded in QGIS software (Dile, et.al., 2016).
- This study utilizes the weather data provided by the open source-based weather stations deployed in Deduru Oya basin. These weather observations are managed and dispatched by the istSOS free and open source sensor observation service. The OAT (Observation Analysis Tool) module (Cannata, et.al, 2016), which is implemented as a plugin for QGIS also allows for processing and manipulation weather observations.
- Due to the unavailability of proper locational information on basin and sub-basin boundary of the case study area, boundary delineation has to do first prior to the model development. SWAT embedded GUIs allow users to delineate the catchment boundaries and sub-basins considering the elevation and stream network of the area.
- Availability of good manuals and user forums to assist in troubleshooting
- An additional interesting aspect of SWAT is the ongoing development that is taking place, with contributions coming from different groups, in different parts of the world.
- Availability of SWAT-CUP standalone for model calibration, validation and uncertainty assessment

5.2 SWAT (Soil and Water Assessment Tool)

SWAT is the acronym for Soil and Water Assessment Tool which was developed by Dr Jeff Arnold for the USDA (United States Department of Agriculture) Agriculture Research Service.

SWAT models the upland processes and channel processes. Figure 2 illustrates the main aspects considered in SWAT model when modelling upland and channel processes.

Figure 2: Hydrological modelling processes considered in the SWAT model

Identification of hydrological processes of the watershed is a prerequisite to perform model calibration. In hydrological models, processes refer to the main parts of the hydrological cycle: precipitation, evapotranspiration, runoff and infiltration. The dynamic processes of hydrological cycle can be represented by equations. SWAT uses the following water balance equation to represent the soil water content at basin level:

$$SW_t = SW_0 + \sum_{i=1}^t (R_{day} - Q_{surf} - E_a - w_{seep} - Q_{gw}) \text{ Equation 4}$$

where SW_t is the final soil water content, SW_0 is the initial soil water content on day i , t is the time, R_{day} is the amount of precipitation on day i , Q_{surf} is the amount of surface runoff on day i , E_a is the amount of evapotranspiration on day i , w_{seep} is the amount of water entering the vadose zone from the soil profile on day i , and Q_{gw} is the amount of return flow on day i .

SWAT model can be operated at monthly, daily, sub-daily and sub-hourly time steps. Most of the simulations done from SWAT are based on hourly, daily, monthly and yearly simulations. SWAT's modeling capability was limited to sub-daily (hourly) time step, prior to the addition of sub-hourly modeling capability in year 2010 (Jeong, et.al, 2010). However, several studies have been shown SWAT's capability of capturing peak flows during flash storms, when running the model under hourly or sub-hourly time steps (Shannak, 2017; Yang, et.al, 2016; Maharjan, et.al, 2013; Li, et.al, 2018; Yu, et.al, 2018; Bauwe, et.al, 2017; Boithias, 2017).

SWAT's algorithms for infiltration, surface runoff, flow routing, impoundments, and lagging of surface runoff have been modified to allow flow simulations with a sub-hourly time interval as

small as one minute and evapotranspiration, soil water contents, base flow, and lateral flow are estimated on a daily basis and distributed equally for each time step (Jeong, et.al, 2010). Therefore, it is adequate to use precipitation at sub-hourly time step while other input data (temperature, relative humidity, solar radiation and wind speed) at daily time step.

As shown in the Figure 3, QSWAT hydrological modelling tool has mainly 4 steps to perform. Since the “Visualize” option only supports visualizing the for yearly, monthly and daily simulation results, running the 4th step is not important in this study. Step 1 and 2 is needed to run only at the beginning of developing the model. Those two steps do not need to run again when uploading new weather data to generate the outputs. The results of the model with respect to the new weather data could be obtained only running the step 3.

Figure 3: QSWAT interface

5.3 Required data to set-up the model

The required data to set-up and run the SWAT model are given in Table 1.

Table 1: Required data for the SWAT model

	Input Data	Source	Resolution
a)	Digital Elevation Model (DEM)	Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM)	1 arc second (approximately 30m)
b)	Stream Network	Produced by the author	1:10,000
c)	Land use	Survey Department of Sri Lanka	1:50,000
d)	Soil	FAO-UNESCO	1:5,000,000

e)	Historical weather data	Climate Forecast System Reanalysis (CFSR)	0.5 degree (approximately 55km) gridded dataset for the period of 1993 to 2013
f)	Time series data on weather	4ONSE main stations	Subbasin level
g)	Stream water levels	4ONSE river gauges	-

The SWAT requires DEM, land use and soil layers to be uploaded into the model in raster format. DEM is originally in raster format. Land use and soil vector layers were converted to raster format of 30m resolution (to the same resolution of the DEM), prior to upload them in the model. According to Waldo Tobler's rule, the detectable size in meters for 1:50,000 scale land use layer is 25m. As the converted resolution is greater than the detectable size, it doesn't bring any negative impacts to the model.

SWAT uses databases to store information related to plant growth and urban land characteristics. These databases include values pertaining to different variables used in the model. Therefore, all the land uses of the study area were assigned under the nearest corresponding SWAT land use class given in Table 2. Figure 4 shows the land uses of the area, which were categorized as per the SWAT's classes.

Table 2: Land uses of the basin and the corresponding SWAT land use category

Land use classes of the basin	SWAT land use class	SWAT code
Built up area	Residential-Medium Density	URMD
Coconut	Coconut	COCO
Chena	Pasture	PAST
Canal, Lagoon, Reservoir, Sea, Stream, Tank, Waterholes	Water	WATR
Forest	Forest - Mixed	FRST
Home gardens	Residential low density	URLD
Marsh	Wetlands – Mixed	WETL
Prawn farms	Wetlands-Non-Forested	WETN
Grassland , Scrub land, Unclassified and other land	Range – Grasses	RNGE
Paddy	Rice	RICE
Rubber	Rubber	RUBR
Sand	Barren land	BARR

Tea	Agricultural land - Generic	AGRL
Rock	South Western Range	SWRN

Figure 4: Land uses of the study area as per the SWAT land use classes

The SWAT land use classes in the study area belongs to two databases related to plant growth and urban land characteristics. The major limitation of the soil layer is its low resolution. SWAT requires a soil layer classified as per the World Soil Classification developed by FAO of UN. The available soil database in Sri Lanka which was produced by the Geological Survey and Mines Bureau (GSMB) (1:50,000 scale) doesn't classify as per the World Soil Classification. Therefore, FAO's soil layer was used in this research (Figure 5). Prior to the application of FAO's soil layer in the SWAT model, the GSMB's soil layer and FAO's soil layer were cross checked with each other in order to verify that the spatial distribution of soil types in both layers were same. Some minor soil types in the GSMB's soil layer were ignored during this comparison.

Figure 5: FAO soil classes of Deduru Oya basin

SWAT model requires two types of weather data: (1) historical weather data on rainfall, temperature, relative humidity, wind speed and solar radiation to calculate some statistical data in the model and (2) weather data to simulate the flows. Installation of 27 4ONSE weather stations in Deduru Oya basin was commenced on 06th March 2018 and completed on 21st July 2018 (Refer D2.5 Experimental monitoring system deployment report). At least 10 years historical weather data is needed to calculate the relevant statistics for the study area. The required data to run the model was obtained from the CFSR (Climate Forecast System Reanalysis) database. This dataset is the result of the close cooperation between two US organizations, the National Centers for Environmental Prediction (NCEP) and the National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR). It is one such dataset which consists of global climate data over 36 years from 1979 to 2014. The database contains 12 data locations which covers the Deduru Oya basin (Figure 6).

Figure 6: CFSR locations of the study area

The relevant statistical data calculated from the CFSR data set are given in Appendix A. These statistics were used only to generate initial condition of the catchment prior to the deployment period. The period where this initial condition is taken to consider is known as warm up period. Most of the hydrological models consider the warm up period which range from one to several years. The SWAT model requires at least one year warm up period to generate the representative initial condition of the catchment. The weather data during this warm up period considered as underuse since they are not utilized in the model to produce any outputs. Although the CFSR data is low in resolution, it doesn't create any impact to the model since they were applied for the warm up period. The relevant sub-daily (hourly) weather data to generate the model outputs were obtained from 4ONSE weather stations. Figure 7 shows the locations of the 4ONSE stations.

Figure 7: 4NSE stations

Prior to use the 4NSE data in the model, the reliability of the data was checked with some reference station's data in Sri Lanka and Switzerland. The analysis revealed that the accuracy of the 4NSE data is very promising (Sudantha, et al., 2018; Strigaro et al., 2019). For the model calibration, water level data was obtained from 4NSE river gauges. The 4NSE daily and hourly water level data at Amunugama river gauge was compared with the water level data obtained from the Irrigation Department's river gauge located at the same place. Figure 8 and 9 show the results of the comparison. The R^2 value is higher (more than 0.9) in both daily and hourly water level data. As shown in Figure 8, a small water level difference of 10 cm was there in the two river gauges due to the deviation of origin values which are located at the bedrock of the stream. Prior to the use of water level data in model calibration, they were converted to flows (m^3/s) using the stage-discharge relationship equations developed by the Irrigation Department. The equations for the sub-catchments are as follows:

- Deduru Oya sub-catchment at Amunugama: $y = 34.408x^{1.7938}$
- Maguru Oya sub-catchment at Maspotha: $y = 5.3727x^{1.4492}$
- Kimbulwana & Hakwatuna Oya sub-catchment (combined flow) at Ethiliyawela: $y = 4.9804x^{2.5847}$

Figure 8: Comparison of water level data at Amumnugama river gauge (a) Daily average values (b) Hourly values

Figure 9: 4ONSE versus Irrigation Department's river gauge (a) Daily average values (b) Hourly values

SWAT model requires 5 types of weather data to run the model. They are, precipitation, maximum and minimum temperature, solar radiation, relative humidity and wind speed. For sub-daily simulation in SWAT, only the precipitation data is required at sub-daily interval. All the other data is required at daily interval. All the aforementioned weather parameters can be obtained from 4ONSE stations, except the solar radiation. Hence, SWAT's weather generator was used to simulate the daily solar radiation data for the respective sub-basin, based on the statistical data calculated for the watershed. The procedure to generate daily values for solar radiation is based on the weakly stationary generating process presented by Matalas (1967).

The weather data required for the model should be stored in txt format. The locational information of the stations should be stored in separate txt files related to four parameters. As shown in Figure 10, pcp is the txt files which contains locational information of the four stations which measure precipitation. ID should be uniquely numbered. p_bat, p_ram, p_par and p_sb are the files which contain precipitation data of the Batalagoda, Rambadagalla, Paragahadeniya and SB Herath stations respectively. LAT and LONG are the latitude and longitude value of the respective station (in decimal degrees). In a similar way, txt files need to prepare for temperature, relative humidity and wind speed parameters. In those files, the same content

inside the pcp file is repeated except the NAME column. An example for this is shown in Figure 11.


```
pcp - Notepad
File Edit Format View Help
ID,NAME,LAT, LONG, ELEVATION
1,p_bat,7.530750,80.438760,119
2,p_ram,7.507700,80.509230,178
3,p_par,7.41561,80.47272,167
4,p_sb,7.65528,80.34604,102
```

Figure 10: The txt files which includes locational information of the stations which measure precipitation


```
tmp - Notepad
File Edit Format View Help
ID,NAME,LAT, LONG, ELEVATION
1,t_bat,7.530750,80.438760,119
2,t_ram,7.507700,80.509230,178
3,t_par,7.41561,80.47272,167
4,t_sb,7.65528,80.34604,102
```

Figure 11: The txt files which includes locational information of the stations which measure temperature

The snippets shown in Figure 12 shows the formats related to precipitation and temperature files related to Batalagoda station. The first row should be kept for entering the starting date (the format should be YYYYMMDD) of the weather data used in the model. The model was developed to simulate hourly outputs. Accordingly, only the precipitation data was entered at hourly interval, while the data of all the other parameters were entered at daily interval. Hence, in the precipitation files, the interval of the data (in minutes) should be mentioned together with the starting date (Figure 12). When entering the temperature data in the txt files, both maximum and minimum temperature values should be entered.

A warm-up period of 2 years (2017 and 2018) was considered when developing the model. The 4ONSE weather data during the period of 1st June to 31st October in 2019 was used to calibrate and validate the model. Hence, "-99" value was applied to the records prior to 1st June 2019 and records beyond 31st October 2019. By applying "-99" value for the missing

data, it is possible to command the model to simulate those missing values through SWAT's weather generator, based on the statistical data calculated for the basin. Unlike other hydrological models, the SWAT doesn't have any option to include value on initial discharge. Since it operates as a continuous model, the initial discharge should be adjusted within the model during the model calibration process. As the model was calibrated for the period after 1st of June 2019, it uses the realtime data of the 4ONSE stations to estimate the flows of the given time of concentration period. Hence putting "-99" for the past missing data (the period before 1st of June 2019) would not create any harm to the model. However, the accuracy of the results is strongly influenced if there's any missing data related to 4ONSE stations during the period after 1st June 2019.

Figure 12: Formats of the precipitation and temperature data files related to Batalagoda station

6 Methodology

6.1 Watershed Delineation

The word 'watershed' is used interchangeably with drainage basin or catchment. It is an area of land that drains all the streams and rainfall to a common outlet such as the outflow of a reservoir, mouth of a bay, ocean or any point along a stream channel. Broadly a watershed has four components: watershed boundary, sub-basins, stream network and outlets (Figure 13). A watershed can have smaller sub-basins that combine to form a larger watershed. The outlets are the points on the surface at which water flows out an area. It is the lowest point along the boundary of a watershed.

Figure 13: Components of watershed

Watershed delineation is the key step to perform in most of the hydrological modelling approaches since it provides valuable inputs on identifying the boundaries in which the surface water runoff divides. Successful and accurate watershed delineation is the precondition of the following runoff, sediment and water quality modeling and credible results (Luo, et.al., 2011).

The watershed boundaries are selected on the basis of topographic information. Traditionally, watershed boundaries have been identified by manually drawing them onto paper topographic maps. The person who draws the lines makes the judgment of where a divide is located in a particular location based on topographic and other information on the map. If the map is incorrect, or if the analyst makes a mistake, the watershed boundaries may be in error. More recent methods use computer programs to delineate watersheds. Topographic contours have been transformed into a grid of numbers (called a Digital Elevation Model, or DEM), where each number represents the land-surface elevation interpolated from the original topographic map. Computer programs delineate watersheds on the basis of DEMs.

Watershed delineation based on Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) is the initial step to perform in SWAT model (Step 1 of Figure 3) . There are two methods for watershed delineation in SWAT model, one is the DEM-based method, which is based on the DEM of the study area and the other is the pre-defined method in which users can define the reaches and sub-basins manually. In this research, DEM based method was used to delineate the watershed of the case study area.

First the DEM was loaded into the SWAT model. Then using the “Burn-in” function, the stream network, digitized by the author was imported and superimposed onto the DEM to define the location of the stream network. “Burn-in” algorithm was first put forwarded by Maidment of University of Texas, US (Luo, et.al., 2011). In this method, available stream network dataset is used to process the DEM: the elevations of the grids overlapped by the digital channel network are reduced by a little value to increase the slopes with other surrounding grids (William & David, 1996).

The stream network layer which used for this process should be a continuous set of stream lines, in which lines should be drawn through tanks, lakes and ponds. The isolated lines should be removed prior to the use them in the model. Further, the stream network should be digitized in a manner in which only one stream segment is shown in between two confluences.

After the “Burn-in” process, the QSWAT model pre-processes the DEM by filling pits, calculating the flow direction, counting the contributing area and finally delineating the watershed. QSWAT uses TauDEM (Terrain Analysis Using Digital Elevation Models) for watershed delineation. It was developed by Utah State University (USU) for hydrologic digital elevation model analysis and watershed delineation. The process of watershed delineation using TauDEM is illustrated in Figure 14.

Figure 14: Process of watershed delineation using TauDEM

The first step of TauDEM analysis is to remove pits (Figure 15). The main idea behind removing pits is to produce hydrologically corrected DEM without any natural and artificial depressions to avoid numerical problems in algorithms associated with gravity flow.

Figure 15: Schematic diagram representing the effect of Pit removal

The next function is to calculate the flow direction to one of its eight adjacent or diagonal neighboring cells. The flow direction coding is as follows: 1–East, 2–North East, 3–North, 4–North West, 5–West, 6–South West, 7–South, 8–South East (Figure 16). In TauDEM, the flow direction routing across flat areas is performed according to the method described by Garbrecht & Martz (1996). Then, the contributing area of each cell is taken by counting number of grid cells draining through each grid cell based on flow direction.

Figure 16: Flow direction coding of TauDEM

The next step of stream network delineation process takes the output of contributing area as input and delineate the stream network for a user defined threshold. This defines a stream raster grid as all grid cells with contributing area greater than a designated threshold. This threshold is defined either as a number of cells (the default is 1% in SWAT) or as a drainage area in square kilometers. Lesser the threshold value, greater the possibility of visualizing every tiny tributary. Hence, for less threshold values, SWAT develops larger number of sub-basins. This makes the model more complex and consumes more time to run the model. Therefore, for this research, the default value of 1% (1% from the total area) was selected as the threshold.

The outlet/s and reservoirs in SWAT should be located in a manner that they should approximately lie on the delineated stream network. The SWAT considers the water bodies located on the stream network, both natural and manmade as 'reservoirs'. There are 8 major reservoirs and 2408 minor reservoirs in the Deduru Oya basin. In this research, only the major reservoirs were taken into consideration when developing the model. Out of the major reservoirs, the largest reservoir, which is the Deduru Oya tank is located center of the basin, two tanks located at the lower basin and the remaining five tanks are located at the upper basin. Since the tank management model of this research is developed for the Deduru Oya tank, the five major tanks in the upper basin are influenced for variation of tank levels in the Deduru Oya reservoir. Out of those five tanks, the tanks which are directly connected with the

stream network were taken when delineating the watershed. Accordingly, Kimbulwana Oya and Hakwatuna Oya are the tanks which are directly connected to the delineated watershed. Hence, Deduru Oya, Kimbulwana Oya and Hakwatuna Oya tanks are located in the SWAT model as reservoirs during the watershed delineation process. Considering the convenience of running the model, the selected reservoirs were taken into a single sub-basin. For that, outlets were located at the places where the streams of the upper basin meet the reservoir and the reservoir point was placed at the outlet of the reservoir. The outlet of the river mouth was located at the place, where the river enters the ocean (Figure 17).

Figure 17: Locations of outlet points and reservoirs

After correctly locating the outlets and reservoirs on the delineated stream network, the Peuker Douglas Methodology (Peuker & Douglas, 1975) was run in the model. This is quite an elaborate function and involves first calculating a grid of stream sources following the Peuker Douglas methodology for identifying valley grid cells. This typically represents a disconnected skeleton like depiction of the stream network. These grid cells are then aggregated using a weighted contributing area calculation to produce the source aggregated grid that is connected like a stream network. The function then goes through a Drop Analysis process to determine an appropriate threshold of the source aggregated grid to be used to map streams and the resulting streams are mapped in the Stream Raster grid. The result is a stream network where drainage density has been objectively determined based on the geomorphology.

The next function is to delineate the watershed. This outputs a watershed divided into several sub-basins. A total of 28 sub-basins were received. To avoid the small sub-basins, the sub-basins which have land area less than 25% of the mean area were selected and merged. In the merging process, sub-basins which have an outlet or reservoir were ignored by the model. The merging process was produced 22 sub-basins for the Deduru Oya watershed area (Figure 18).

Figure 18: Delineated sub-basins of Deduru Oya Basin

6.2 Creating Hydrological Response Units (HRUs)

Sub-basins in SWAT further divided into homogeneous areas called Hydrological Response Units (HRUs). HRU is the total area in the sub-basin with a particular land use, soil and slope. Individual fields with a specific land use, soil and slope are lumped together to form one HRU. HRUs simplify the SWAT run by lumping all similar soil, land use and slope areas into a single response unit. Implicit in the concept of the HRU is the assumption that there is no interaction between HRUs in one basin loadings (runoff with sediment, nutrients transported by the runoff) from each HRU are calculated separately and then summed together to determine the total loadings from the sub-basin (Arnold, et al., 2012).

During the HRU creating process, the slope of the study area was classified into four classes in the range of 0–11%, 11–33%, 33–86% and above 86%, considering the natural breaks of slope values. Slope is an important factor in SWAT which determines the water movement. Figure 19 shows the snippet of the generated HRU report.

Landuse/Soil/slope and HRU Distribution 03 May 2018 14.40
 Using percentage of subbasin as a threshold
 Multiple HRUs Landuse/Soil/slope option Thresholds: 0/0/0 [%]
 Number of HRUs: 845
 Number of subbasins: 22

Numbers in parentheses are corresponding values before HRU creation

watershed		Area [ha]		261281.12	
Landuse		Area [ha]		%watershed	
COCO		113878.02	(113878.02)	43.58	(43.58)
RICE		54837.74	(54837.74)	20.99	(20.99)
URLD		44279.23	(44279.23)	16.95	(16.95)
WATR		12107.58	(12107.58)	4.63	(4.63)
RNGE		18942.25	(18942.25)	7.25	(7.25)
RUBR		4940.90	(4940.90)	1.89	(1.89)
AGRL		349.04	(349.04)	0.13	(0.13)
FRST		6887.47	(6887.47)	2.64	(2.64)
SWRN		2084.34	(2084.34)	0.80	(0.80)
PAST		2624.59	(2624.59)	1.00	(1.00)
BARR		2.63	(2.63)	0.00	(0.00)
WETL		225.57	(225.57)	0.09	(0.09)
URMD		55.05	(55.05)	0.02	(0.02)
WETN		66.72	(66.72)	0.03	(0.03)
soil					
Lc71-2b		150010.56	(150010.56)	57.41	(57.41)
Lc72-2a		2167.53	(2167.53)	0.83	(0.83)
Qc50-1a		3125.05	(3125.05)	1.20	(1.20)
Jd5-2-3a		3233.74	(3233.74)	1.24	(1.24)
Lc73-2bc		8069.43	(8069.43)	3.09	(3.09)
Af45-2b		58464.93	(58464.93)	22.38	(22.38)
Bf12-3bc		36209.89	(36209.89)	13.86	(13.86)
Slope					
0-11.11		206529.96	(206529.96)	79.05	(79.05)
11.11-33.21		37557.48	(37557.48)	14.37	(14.37)
33.21-86.13		15557.19	(15557.19)	5.95	(5.95)
86.13-9999		1636.49	(1636.49)	0.63	(0.63)

Figure 19: Snippet of the HRU report

6.3 Hydrological processes in SWAT model

Table 3 shows the options available in SWAT model to simulate the main hydrological processes. Accordingly, the Penman-Monteith method, Green & Ampt method, Soil moisture method and Muskingham Cunge method were applied to simulate the hydrological processes of potential evapotranspiration, runoff routing, daily-curve number calculation and channel flow respectively.

Table 3: Options in SWAT model to simulate the hydrologic processes

Process	Options
Potential Evapotranspiration Estimation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Penman – Monteith Priestly – Taylor Hargreaves
Runoff	Rainfall / runoff / routing option <ul style="list-style-type: none"> SCS curve number Green and Ampt Mein Larson
	Daily curve number (CN) calculation method <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Soil moisture method Plant ET method
Channel flow	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Variable storage coefficient Muskingham Cunge

During the modelling process, it was found Plant ET method and Muskingham method is more appropriate in modelling the runoff and channel flow respectively. SWAT provides two methods for estimating surface runoff: the SCS curve number (CN) method (SCS, 1972) and the Green and Ampt Mein Larson (GAML) excess rainfall method (Mein and Larson, 1973). CN method is an empirical model, which is based on rainfall-runoff relationships of different land uses and soil types in USA. GAML method is a physically based model, which considers direct relationship between infiltration and rainfall based on physical parameters allowing continuous surface runoff simulation (Jeong, et.al, 2010). Garen and Moore (2005) revealed, CN method is not suitable for simulating the continuous surface runoff at sub-hourly interval, since it estimates the direct runoff using empirical relationships between the total rainfall and watershed properties. King et al. (1999) also suggests GAML is more appropriate for sub-hourly simulation than CN method, due to its less biasness over model prediction. Further, several studies (Shannak, 2017; Yang,et.al, 2016; Maharjan, et.al, 2013; Li,et.al, 2018; Yu,et.al, 2018; Bauwe, et.al, 2017; Boithias, 2017) have revealed the better performance of GAML in simulating the peak flows during flashy storms. Hence, GAML method has been chosen for sub-hourly surface runoff simulation.

6.4 Model calibration and validation

The performance of the hydrological model was assessed during the model calibration and validation process. In this study, the streamflow data measured at the river gauges of the upper watershed was used to assess the model performance. The Deduru Oya reservoir which is the selected tank for this study is located at the center of the Deduru Oya basin. Therefore, the runoff generated at the upper sub-basins mainly controls the water level of the Deduru Oya reservoir. As shown in Figure 20, these upper sub-basins further cluster into four sub-catchments based on the four streams which start from the upper watershed and merged at the Deduru Oya reservoir.

Figure 21 shows the discharge at Amunugama, Maspotha and Ethiliyagala River gauges which measure the stream flow of Deduru Oya, Maguru Oya and the combined flow of Hakwatuna Oya & Kimbulwana Oya respectively. These river gauges belong to Irrigation Department of Sri Lanka. The discharge of year 2015, 2017 and 2018 data are illustrated here (the discharge of year 2016 was not plotted here due to the missing data). Accordingly, the reservoir receives largest inflow from Deduru Oya stream especially during the periods of February to May and September to December. The combined flows of Hakwatuna and Kimbulwana sub-catchments and Maguru Oya sub-catchments are approximately 1/3rd of the Deduru Oya flow.

Figure 20: Sub-catchments of upper watershed

Figure 21: Discharge measured at Amunugama, Maspotha & Ethiliyagala river gauges during the year 2015, 2017 & 2018

For the convenience of calibrating the model, the sub-catchments were separately calibrated by uploading the 4ONSE weather data. Figure 22 shows the relevant 4ONSE weather stations belong to each sub catchment.

Figure 22: Relevant 4ONSE weather stations belong to each sub-catchment

To calibrate the model, SWAT-CUP (SWAT Calibration and Uncertainty Procedures) open source application, which was particularly designed for SWAT models was used. Prior to calibrate the model, the water level data (in meters) was converted to flows (in m³/s) using the stage discharge relationship equations generated by the Irrigation Department. SWAT-CUP contains several methods to calibrate the model. They are:

- 1) SUFI-2 (Abbaspour et.al, 2015)
- 2) GLUE (Beven and Binley, 1992)
- 3) ParaSol (Van Griensven and Meixner, 2006)
- 4) MCMC (Kuczera and Parent, 1998)
- 5) PSO (Eberhart and Kennedy, 1995)

In this study, an Inverse Modeling approach of SUFI-2 (Sequential Uncertainties Fitting Version 2) algorithm was used to calibrate the model. It follows a stochastic modelling approach, where range of values are applied to parameters instead of single values. Hence, the uncertainties in the model with reference to the parameters can be expressed as ranges.

There are several objective functions available in SWAT-CUP to determine the fitness of the model statistically. These objective functions measures of how well a model simulation fits the

available observations (Beven , 2001). In this study, Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency (NSE) method was used. The objective function proposed by Nash and Sutcliffe (1970) is defined in Equation 5. The NSE value ranges between $-\infty$ and 1. It indicates the match between observed and predicted values. Values between 0 – 1 are generally viewed as acceptable levels of performance, whereas values less than 0 indicate unacceptable performance.

$$\text{Maximize : } \quad NSE = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (O_i - \bar{O})^2 - \sum_{i=1}^n (P_i - O_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (O_i - \bar{O})^2} \quad \text{Equation 5}$$

In addition, SWAT-CUP also measures the goodness of fit (R^2), which ranges between 0 and 1 (Equation 6). This indicates the proportion of the variance in the measured data. The higher values indicate less error variance. Usually, $R^2 > 0.5$ is considered acceptable (Santhi, et.al., 2001; Van Liew, et.al., 2003).

$$R^2 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (O_i - \bar{O})(P_i - \bar{P})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (O_i - \bar{O})^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (P_i - \bar{P})^2}} \quad \text{Equation 6}$$

Where n is the number of observations in the period under consideration, O_i is the i^{th} observed value, \bar{O} is the mean observed value, P_i is the i^{th} model-predicted value and \bar{P} is the mean model predicted value.

In SUFI-2 algorithm, the fit between the simulated result and the observed values are expressed as 95PPU – 95% prediction uncertainty. Each simulation produces two statistics: P-factor and R-factor. P-factor is the percentage of observed data simulated in the model. Hence, $(1 - P \text{ factor})$ is the percentage of observed data not simulated well in the model, in other words “model error”. R-factor is the thickness of the 95PPU envelop. It is calculated as follows:

$$R - \text{factor} = \frac{\frac{1}{n_j} \sum_{t=1}^{n_j} (x_s^{t_i, 97.5\%} - x_s^{t_i, 2.5\%})}{\sigma_{oj}} \quad \text{Equation 7}$$

Where $x_s^{t_i, 97.5\%}$ and $x_s^{t_i, 2.5\%}$ are the upper and lower boundary of the 95PPU at time step t and simulation t .

For model outputs related to discharge, SWAT-CUP recommends P-factor greater than 70%, while having R-factor of around 1. It gives the P-factor and R-factor of the best simulation. SWAT tool becomes a stochastic hydrological model, when using SWAT-CUP for model calibration. Each iteration of the model selects the best parameter values and their ranges. Model parameters cannot have a single value due to their diversity and temporal variation. Further, the selected model calibration algorithm of this study, which is SUFI-2, is an inverse modeling approach. Hence, the measured observations can be produced with different parameter sets. Hence, the best way to show the modeling result is by means of parameter distributions which fit with the observed data. If the model result is unsatisfactory, another iteration can be made using the new parameter ranges produced in the previous iteration.

Thanks to the 4ONSE project, a dense weather station network has been established in the Deduru Oya river basin. Having a dense network, allows modellers to use data of the nearby

stations when there are any issues related to continuity of the dataset in some stations. However, different parameterization schemes need to be employed to the model when applying data of different weather stations. For an example, compared to other 3 sub-catchments, the Deduru Oya sub-catchment has 5 subbasins with diversified topographic and landuse variation. Seven 4ONSE weather stations have been deployed there. A modeller can use all the seven stations or only one station to run the model.

SWAT uses the weather data in the model at sub-basin level. When there are more than 1 station in a particular sub-basin, SWAT obtains the weather data for that subbasin from the station which locates near to its sub-basin's centroid. If only one station's weather data is used for the entire sub-catchment, the model assumes all the sub-basins in that particular sub-catchment have similar weather condition. Accordingly, for Deduru Oya sub-catchment, the model was tested with 2 types of weather datasets considering the continuity of the data. They are:

1. Application of data of 4 stations - Paragahadeniya-PCB, Rambadagalla-PCB, Batalagoda-MOD and SB Herath-MOD
2. Application of data of only one station – Batalagoda-MOD

The data during the period of 1st June to 31st October 2019 was used in the model. The basin had a dry weather condition with sporadic rainfall pattern during the months of June and July. While the basin area received a comparatively frequent rainfall during the months of August to October. Therefore, the model was tested under both dry and wet weather conditions.

As shown in Table 4, SWAT usually has many parameters to simulate the processes related to evapotranspiration, surface runoff, time of concentration, transmission losses from surface runoff, soil water, lateral flow, groundwater flow and channel water routing. The definitions of these parameters are given in Appendix B.

Table 4: Parameters related to SWAT hydrological processes

SWAT Process	Related parameters
Potential and actual evapotranspiration	ESCO, EPCO, CANMX, SOL_ALB, GW_REVAP, REVAPMN
Surface runoff	CNCOEF, SURLAG, CN2
Time of concentration	CH_L(1), CH_S(1), CH_N(1), SLSUBBSN, OV_N
Crack flow	SOL_CRK
Soil water	FFCB, SOL_Z, SOL_BD, SOL_AWC, SOL_K
Lateral flow	HRU_SLP, LAT_TTIME, SLSOIL
Groundwater	SHALLST, DEEPST, GW_DELAY, ALPHA_BF, GWQMN, GW_REVAP, REVAPMN, RCHRG_DP, WUSHAL, WUDEEP
Channel water routing	TRNSRCH, EVRCH, MSK_CO1, MSK_CO2, MSK_X, CH_W(2), CH_D, CH_S(2), CH_L(2), CH_N(2), CH_K(2), ALPHA_BNK

SWAT automatically calculates some of the above parameters considering the land use, soil and elevation data uploaded in to the model. Therefore, initially the model was run using these default parameter values and the output received from this initial run was uploaded in to the SWAT-CUP for calibrating the model. The initial step of model calibration is to identify the dominant parameters related to each sub-catchment. SWAT-CUP uses following scheme to parameterize / regionalize the parameters of a watershed:

$x_<parname>.<ext>_<hydrogrp>_<soltext>_<landuse>_<subbasn>_<slope>$

In this scheme, $x_<parname>$ represents the type of change to be applied to the parameter. There are three types of changes that can be applied:

- 1) $V_<parname>$ - replacing the existing parameter value
- 2) $A_<parname>$ - given value is added to the existing parameter value
- 3) $R_<parname>$ - existing parameter (spatial parameters) value if multiplied by $(1 + \text{given value})$

$<parname>$ represents the SWAT parameter name as it appears in the SWAT Input Output manual. $<ext>$ is the SWAT file extension code for the file containing in the parameter. $<hydrogrp>$, $<soltext>$, $<landuse>$, $<subbasn>$ and $<slope>$ are the filters used in this scheme, which represent soil hydrolocal group, soil texture, land use, sub-basin number and slope respectively.

To identify the dominant parameters, SWAT-CUP's One-at-a-time (OAT) local sensitivity analysis was performed. OAT shows sensitivity of a variable to the changes in a parameter if all the other parameters are kept constant at some value. OAT analysis was performed taking minimum of three simulations. As an example, Figure 23 shows the results of the OAT sensitivity analysis related to CN2 (Initial SCS runoff curve number for moisture condition II) parameter. Since CN2 is a spatial parameter, the relative change was applied with -0.2(min) to 0.2(max) range. In Figure 23, the green colour line shows the simulated stream flow with no change to the default CN2 value. The blue colour line and brown colour line shows the simulated flow after the multiplying the default CN2 value by 1.1333 ($1+0.1333$) and 0.8667 ($1 - 0.1333$) respectively. Accordingly, the graph illustrated in Figure 23 clearly shows the change of simulated flow with respect to the variation of CN2 value. Accordingly, CN2 parameter can be considered as a significant parameter. The same principle was applied when identifying other dominant parameters of the model.

Figure 23: Results of the OAT sensitivity analysis related to CN2 parameter

Accordingly, 13, 10, 11 parameters have been discovered as the dominant parameters for Deduru Oya sub-catchment, Maguru Oya sub-catchment and Kimbulwana Oya sub-catchment respectively. The model calibration was performed, considering only these parameters. Out of the four catchments, the total runoff generated Hakwatuna sub-catchment collected at the Moragoda anicut and distributed to surrounding agricultural lands. Therefore, only a small portion of flow is received to the Deduru Oya reservoir from there. Accordingly, the Hakwatuna sub-catchment doesn't make a significant contribution to the inflow of Deduru Oya reservoir. During the rainfall events, the discharge from the Hakwatuna and Kimbulwana oya sub-catchments could be controlled to a certain extent through the Moragoda anicut and Hakwatuna Oya & Kimbulwana Oya tanks. Further, it was unable to find hourly tank release data related to Hakwatuna Oya & Kimbulwana Oya tanks. Hence, the model calibration and validation could not be performed to Hakwatuna & Kimbulwana Oya sub-catchments. Therefore, calibration and validation were performed only to remaining two sub-catchments. Out of those two sub-catchments, Deduru Oya is the major determinant in managing the water level of the reservoir during the heavy rainfalls.

Tables 5, 6 and 7 show the sensitive parameters received for Deduru Oya, Maguru Oya and Kimbulwana Oya sub-catchments respectively, after performing the OAT sensitivity analysis.

Table 5: Sensitive parameters of Deduru Oya sub-catchment

Parameter	Name of the Parameter	Type of change	Category
SOL_BD	Moist bulk density	Replaced	Soil parameter
MSK_X	Weighting factor that controls the relative importance of inflow and outflow in determining the storge in reach	Replaced	Watershed level parameter

MSK_CO1	Calibration coefficient used to control the impact of the storage time constant for normal flow	Replaced	Watershed level parameter
MSK_CO2	Calibration coefficient used to control the impact of the storage time constant for low flow	Replaced	Watershed level parameter
ALPHA_BF	Baseflow alpha factor	Replaced	Groundwater parameter
SOL_K	Saturated hydraulic conductivity	Replaced	Soil parameter
CN2	Initial SCS runoff curve number for moisture condition II	Multiplied	HRU management level parameter
SURLAG	Surface runoff lag coefficient	Replaced	HRU level parameter
GW_REVAP	Groundwater "revap" coefficient	Replaced	Groundwater parameter
CH_K2	Effective hydraulic conductivity in main channel alluvium	Replaced	Water routing parameter
CH_N1	Manning's "n" value for the tributary channels	Replaced	Sub-basin level parameter
CH_N2	Manning's "n" value for the main channel	Replaced	Water routing parameter
GWQMN	Threshold depth of water in the shallow aquifer required for return flow to occur	Multiplied	Groundwater parameter

Table 6: Sensitive parameters of Maguru Oya sub-catchment

Parameter	Name of the Parameter	Type of change	Category
CN2	Initial SCS runoff curve number for moisture condition II	Multiplied	HRU management level parameter
SOL_BD	Moist bulk density	Multiplied	Soil parameter
ESCO	Soil evaporation compensation factor	Replaced	Soil parameter

GW_DELAY	Groundwater delay time	Replaced	Groundwater parameter
ALPHA_BF	Baseflow alpha factor	Replaced	Groundwater parameter
SOL_K	Saturated hydraulic conductivity	Replaced	Soil parameter
GWQMN	Threshold depth of water in the shallow aquifer required for return flow to occur	Replaced	Groundwater parameter
GW_REVAP	Groundwater "revap" coefficient	Replaced	Groundwater parameter
CH_N2	Manning's "n" value for the main channel	Replaced	Water routing parameter
SURLAG	Surface runoff lag coefficient	Replaced	HRU level parameter

Table 7: Sensitive parameters of Kimbulwana Oya sub-catchment

Parameter	Name of the Parameter	Type of change	Category
GW_DELAY	Groundwater delay time	Multiplied	Groundwater parameter
GWQMN	Threshold depth of water in the shallow aquifer required for return flow to occur	Replaced	Groundwater parameter
CN2	Initial SCS runoff curve number for moisture condition II	Multiplied	HRU management level parameter
RES_K	Hydraulic conductivity of the reservoir bottom	Replaced	Reservoir parameter
CH_N2	Manning's "n" value for the main channel	Replaced	Water routing parameter
SOL_BD	Moist bulk density	Multiplied	Soil parameter
SOL_AWC	Available water capacity of the soil layer	Multiplied	Soil parameter
ESCO	Soil evaporation compensation factor	Replaced	Soil parameter
SOL_K	Saturated hydraulic conductivity	Multiplied	Soil parameter
CH_K2	Effective hydraulic conductivity in main channel alluvium	Replaced	Water routing parameter

ALPHA_BF	Baseflow alpha factor	Replaced	Groundwater parameter
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Before calibrating the model for hourly basis, the model was regionalized first, using the daily 4ONSE data. During the daily simulation it was observed that the baseflow is too low and the discharge was shifted to left. It was corrected by changing the parameters given in Table 8. The changed parameter values were applied then for the hourly simulation.

Table 8: Regionalized parameters

Simulated condition	Applied change for the parameters
Baseflow too low	Reduced the GWQMN Reduced the GW_REVAP
Discharge shift to left	Increased the CH_N2

When applying data of 4 stations for the Deduru Oya sub-catchment, CANMX (maximum canopy storage) parameter was also received as sensitive for the dominant land use categories (Coconut, Rice, Rubber, Low density residential areas) of the sub-catchment. Since CANMX is a parameter which introduces water to the system, it was fixed first by calibrating the model at daily time step. Table 9 shows the CANMX parameter values with respect to the dominant land use categories. These values were then uploaded to the hourly model.

Table 9: CANMX values with respect to dominant land use categories

Landuse category	CANMX value (mm)
Coconut	95
Rice	71
Low density residential	43
Rubber	43

Then using the sensitive parameters identified in the OAT analysis the model the model was iterated 4 times and check the results. In this study, 500 simulations were made under each iteration. Table 10 and Figures 24 -30 show the observed and simulated results related to sub-catchments. The periods that the stations were unable to count the rainfall records were removed to obtain a better result from the model.

Table 10: Results on model performance

Sub-catchment	Period	Daily / Hourly	Number of stations used	P factor	R factor	R²	NS
----------------------	---------------	-----------------------	--------------------------------	-----------------	-----------------	----------------------	-----------

Deduru Oya Sub-catchment	1 st to 15 th June 2019	Hourly	04	0.96	0.76	0.76	0.75
	15 th to 30 th June 2019	Hourly	04	0.96	0.89	0.89	0.88
	4 th to 9 th August 2019	Hourly	04	1.0	0.53	0.77	0.55
	1 st to 15 th August 2019	Hourly	04	0.74	0.54	0.67	0.63
	1 st to 15 th August 2019	Hourly	01	0.78	0.57	0.63	0.61
	16 th to 23 rd August 2019	Hourly	04	0.83	0.00	0.67	0.43
Maguru Oya Sub-catchment	1 st to 28 th August 2019	Daily	01	0.82	1.02	0.71	0.69
	23 rd to 27 th August 2019	Hourly	01	0.70	7.56	0.59	-0.82

Figure 24: Observed and Simulated hourly flow for Deduru Oya sub-catchment during the period of 1st to 15th June 2019 – applied data of 4 stations

Figure 25: Observed and Simulated hourly flow for Deduru Oya sub-catchment during the period of 4th to 9th August 2019 - applied data of 4 stations

Figure 26: Observed and Simulated hourly flow for Deduru Oya sub-catchment during the period of 1st to 15th August 2019 - applied data of 4 stations

Figure 27: Observed and Simulated hourly flow for Deduru Oya sub-catchment during the period of 1st to 15th August 2019 - applied data of 1 station

Figure 28: Observed and Simulated hourly flow for Deduru Oya sub-catchment during the period of 16th to 23rd August 2019 - applied data of 4 stations

Figure 29: Observed and Simulated daily flow for Maguru Oya sub-catchment during the period of 1st to 28th August 2019 - applied data of 1 station

Figure 30: Observed and Simulated hourly flow for Maguru Oya sub-catchment during the period of 23rd to 27th August 2019 - applied data of 1 station

Table 11 shows parameter ranges which can be also called as uncertainty range of parameters obtained for the Deduru Oya sub-catchment. Figure 31 shows the variation of parameter values during the dry and wet periods which were taken for calibration and validation. Since the SUFI2 algorithm used in the SWAT-CUP calibration assessment tool follows a stochastic modelling approach, the model cannot be run using a single parameter set. Hydrological parameters cause for changes, due to the continuous changes in the climatic and geographic processes. As per the Figure 31 and Table 12, the parameters such as MSK_X, MSK_CO1, ALPHA_BF, CN2 and GW_REVAP have shown very slight variation (more or less remain unchanged), while the remaining parameters have shown significant variations during the dry and wet periods. The symbol V and R given in front of the parameters denote the type change

applied for the parameter (V for replacing the parameter value by the given value and R for multiplying the parameter value by 1+ given value).

Table 11: Parameter ranges (uncertainty range of parameters) of Deduru Oya sub-catchment

No	Parameter	Parameter range
(1)	V_SOL_BD	1.2 – 3.6
(2)	V_MSK_X	0 – 0.1
(3)	V_MSK_CO1	1.0 – 5.2
(4)	V_MSK_CO2	0 – 8.1
(5)	V_ALPHA_BF	0 – 0.2
(6)	V_SOL_K	5.1 – 21.1
(7)	R_CN2	(-0.3) – 0.1
(8)	V_SURLAG	(-0.5) – 1.0
(9)	V_GW_REVAP	0.1 – 0.2
(10)	V_CH_K2	1.1 – 27.3
(11)	V_CH_N1	(-0.3) – 0.7
(12)	V_CH_N2	0 – 0.7
(13)	R_GWQMN	0.8 – 2.0

Figure 31: Variation of parameter values during the dry and wet periods in Deduru Oya sub-catchment

Table 12: Parameter values received for dry and wet periods

Parameter	Dry period		Wet period				
V__SOL_BD(..).sol	3.4	3.3	1.5	1.6	1.6	1.6	1.6
V__MSK_X.bsn	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
V__MSK_CO1.bsn	4.3	3.0	3.4	3.2	3.2	3.2	1.8
V__MSK_CO2.bsn	7.4	5.7	1.2	1.5	1.5	1.5	0.4
V__ALPHA_BF.gw	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
V__SOL_K(..).sol	7.1	5.4	21.1	13.9	13.9	13.9	21.1
R__CN2.mgt	0.0	0.0	0.0	-0.1	-0.1	-0.1	-0.3
V__SURLAG.hru	0.3	0.4	0.8	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.2
V__GW_REVAP.gw	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
V__CH_K2.rte	11.5	11.2	24.8	17.4	17.4	17.4	26.1
V__CH_N1.sub	0.5	0.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
V__CH_N2.rte	0.0	0.3	0.5	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6
R__GWQMN.gw	1.8	1.7	0.8	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9

As per the statistical results given in Table 10, the performance of the model in simulating the hydrological processes is satisfactory. The fitness of the model is relatively higher when applying weather data of several stations than running the model with single station data. The Davis rain gauge used in the 4ONSE weather stations usually have an error percentage of $\pm 4\%$ for rain rates up to 50mm/hour and $\pm 5\%$ for rain rates within the range of 50mm/hr to 100mm/hr. This is the main causative factor for some of the peaks that the model was unable to reach to its level. Since the model operates in hourly basis, the continuity of the data in the 4ONSE stations is also significantly affect for the model's performance.

7 Application of the hydrological model for the tank management

7.1 Calculating the inflow of the Deduru Oya reservoir

The expected water capacity of the Deduru Oya reservoir at a particular hour could be calculated as shown in Equation 8.

$$C_E = C_0 + 3600(I_D + I_M + I_K + I_H) \quad \text{Equation 8}$$

Where, C_t is the expected capacity, C_0 is the existing capacity, I_D is the inflow to the reservoir from Deduru Oya stream, I_M is the inflow to the reservoir from Maguru Oya stream, I_K is the inflow to the reservoir from Kimbulwana Oya stream and I_H is the inflow to the reservoir from Hakwatuna Oya stream. The hydrological model calculates the inflow to the reservoir in m^3/s . Accordingly, to find the inflow to the reservoir within one hour, it is required to multiply the total inflow value by 3600.

Table 13 shows the approximate time of concentrations of 4 sub-catchments, which is the time needed for water to flow from the most remote point in a watershed to its outlet (Haan, et.al, 1994). Hence, by uploading the realtime weather data to the model, it is possible to estimate the inflow to the reservoir within the given time of concentration period.

Table 13: Time of concentration values of 4 sub-catchments

Sub-catchment	Time of concentration
Deduru Oya	6 hours
Maguru Oya	2 hours
Kimbulwana Oya	2 hours
Hakwatuna Oya	1 & ½ hours

The steps given below elaborates the process of calculating the inflow to the reservoir by applying 4ONSE weather data.

(1) Step 1 – Filling the weather data files in the model with real time 4ONSE data

As explained in section 5.3, the model requires 4 weather parameters (rainfall, maximum and minimum temperature, relative humidity and wind speed) to run the model. The rainfall data obtained from istSOS should be customized to hourly interval before uploading them into the model. Other parameters should be in daily interval. The default model contains 4ONSE weather data during the period of 1st June 2019 to 31st October 2019. Follow the below steps when uploading 4ONSE data after 31st October 2019. Currently, the weather files of the model are filled with “-99” value for the period after 31st October 2019. Those values should be replaced with new data when running the model for the future.

To upload new rainfall data to the model, open the relevant station file and go to the relevant record where you want to start uploading rainfall data. To find the row number to start entering the data, the following equation can be used. The number of the day in that year can be obtained from the table given in Appendix C.

$$17521 + (\text{previous number of day of that year} \times 24) + \text{hour} \quad \text{Equation 9}$$

Example: Row number related to 1st December 2019 at 02:00 is,

$$17521 + (335 \times 24) + 2 = 25563$$

The Equation 9 is valid only for finding the relevant precipitation file's row number for year 2019. For year 2020, another 8760 should be added to the equation. 8760 is the total number of hourly records per year. The reason for using 17521 value in Equation 9 is the use of 2 years of warm period (8760 x 2) in the model with 1st row reserved for starting date of the model.

The Equation 10 should be used to find the relevant row number of the other weather parameters (relative humidity, temperature, wind speed) at daily timestep.

$$731 + \text{number of the day of that year} \quad \text{Equation 10}$$

Like in Equation 9, the Equation 10 also valid only for finding the other weather files row numbers for year 2019. For year 2020, another 365 should be added to the equation. 365 is the total number of daily records per year. The reason for using 731 value in Equation 10 is the used of 2 years of warm period (365 x 2) in the model with 1st row reserved for starting date of the model.

(2) Step 2 – Uploading the weather data files into the model

After filling the weather data files, click on the "Edit Inputs and Run SWAT" button (Refer Figure 3) in QSWAT window to open the "SWAT Editor". Do the following steps to upload the weather data files to the model.

Click on "Connect to databases" → Go to "Write Input Tables" menu → Select "Weather Stations" → Go to "Weather Generator Data" tab → Select "WGEN Deduru" from "Locations Table" → Go to "Rainfall Data" tab → Click on the option "Raingauges" → Select "Precip Timestep as "Sub-Daily" give the Timestep as "60" and browse to the "pcp.txt" file → Then go to the "Temperature Data" tab → Click on the option "Climate Stations" → Browse to the "tmp.txt" file → Do the same for Relative Humidity and Wind speed data → Then go to "Solar Radiation Data" tab and select the "Simulation" option → Click "OK"

(3) Step 3 – Writing the input files

Click on the "Write Input Tables" menu of SWAT Editor → Select "Write SWAT Input Tables" → Click on "Select All" button → Click on "Create Tables" → Except the message on "Use weather database to calculate heat units to maturity (US only)?", for all the other messages select "Yes"

After writing the SWAT Input Tables, the model may arrange its settings to default options provided for hydrological simulation. To change them, go to the "Edit SWAT Input" menu of SWAT Editor → Go to "Watershed Data" → Select "General Data (.BSN)" → Apply the following options given in Table 14.

Table 14: Options need to apply in the model for hourly simulation

Hydrologic Process	Option need to select
Rainfall – Runoff Method	Sub-daily/G&A/Hourly Route (1)

ICN	Soil Moisture Method
Channel Routing	Muskingum

After applying the above option, click on "Save Edits" button → Click on "Exit" button

If needed, the parameters can be changed. For that, go to "SWAT Simulation" menu in SWAT editor → Select "Manual Calibration Helper" → the relevant sensitive parameters found through the SWAT-CUP can be selected from "Select Parameter" drop down menu → Then the relevant change (multiplying / adding / replacing) can be applied from the "Mathematical Op" menu → The parameter value can be entered in "Value" text box → The four filters (Subbasins, Land Use, Soil, Slope) can be applied at the end → Finally update each sensitive parameter by clicking "Update Parameter" button

The Figure 32 shows an example of applying the CANMX parameter value for HRUs contain Coconut land use. The CANMX values obtained during the model calibration process are given in Table 9. Since CANMX is a parameter sensitive only for Deduru Oya sub-catchment, the subbasins' numbers (numbers 7, 9, 11, 15 & 16) of the Deduru Oya sub-catchment were only selected. The relevant sub-basin numbers are labelled in Figure 18.

Figure 32: An example of applying CANMX value for HRUs contain with Coconut landuse in Deduru Oya sub-catchment

After parameterization, go to "Edit SWAT Input" menu in "SWAT Editor" window → select "Re-Write SWAT Input Files"

(4) Step 4 – Run the model

To run the model, go to "SWAT Simulation" menu in "SWAT Editor" window → Select "Run SWAT" → Give the "Starting Date" and "Ending Date" → Select the "SWAT.exe" Version as

"64 bit, release" → Select the option "Daily" and give the "NYSKIP" (Number of Years to Skip) as "2" in the "Printout Settings" → Click on "Setup SWAT Run" button → After that click on "Run SWAT" button

(5) Step 5 – Read the SWAT Output

Go to the "SWAT Simulation" menu in "SWAT Editor" → Select "Read SWAT Output" → Check the "output.rch" → Click the button "Import Files to Database" → The relevant simulation can also be saved separately by giving a name in the bottom text box and by clicking the button "Save Simulation"

To view the output file, go the relevant project folder and open the "Scenarios" folder → Go to the "Default" folder or the folder that you saved separately in the above step → Open the "TxtInOut" folder → Open the file.CIO → Change the "IPRINT" to "3" and save the file → Double click on the "SWAT_64rel" execution file in the TxtInOut folder (If the SWAT_64rel is not in the TxtInOut folder, copy it from the SWAT's SWAT Editor folder and paste it inside the TxtInOut folder) → Double click on the "output.rch" file in the TxtInOut folder to view the results.

By filtering the relevant reach (RCH) numbers (the numbers of the streams which provide water to the Deduru Oya reservoir), the total outflow (Figure 33) from the upper streams to the Deduru Oya reservoir can be calculated. As per the Figure 33, RCH numbers of the upper streams are mentioned in Table 15.

Table 15: Model's RCH numbers related to upper stream network of Deduru Oya basin

RCH number	Stream
10	Maguru Oya
16	Deduru Oya
17	Combined streams of Kimbulwana and Hakwatuna Oya

```

output - Notepad
File Edit Format View Help
1
  SWAT May 20 2015   VER 2015/Rev 637

  General Input/Output section (file.cio):
  10/8/2019 12:00:00 AM ARCGIS-SWAT interface AV

RCH   GIS   DAY   DET   AREAkm2   FLOW_INcms   FLOW_OUTcms   EVAPcms
REACH 1     0     1     1  0.5674E+03  0.3110E+02  0.3097E+02  0.3686E+00
REACH 1     0     1     2  0.5674E+03  0.3109E+02  0.3096E+02  0.3686E+00
REACH 1     0     1     3  0.5674E+03  0.3108E+02  0.3096E+02  0.3686E+00
REACH 1     0     1     4  0.5674E+03  0.3107E+02  0.3096E+02  0.3686E+00
REACH 1     0     1     5  0.5674E+03  0.3106E+02  0.3095E+02  0.3686E+00
REACH 1     0     1     6  0.5674E+03  0.3104E+02  0.3095E+02  0.3686E+00
REACH 1     0     1     7  0.5674E+03  0.3103E+02  0.3095E+02  0.3686E+00
REACH 1     0     1     8  0.5674E+03  0.3101E+02  0.3094E+02  0.3686E+00
REACH 1     0     1     9  0.5674E+03  0.3100E+02  0.3094E+02  0.3686E+00
REACH 1     0     1    10  0.5674E+03  0.3098E+02  0.3094E+02  0.3686E+00
REACH 1     0     1    11  0.5674E+03  0.3096E+02  0.3093E+02  0.3686E+00
REACH 1     0     1    12  0.5674E+03  0.3094E+02  0.3093E+02  0.3686E+00
REACH 1     0     1    13  0.5674E+03  0.3093E+02  0.3092E+02  0.3686E+00
REACH 1     0     1    14  0.5674E+03  0.3091E+02  0.3092E+02  0.3686E+00
REACH 1     0     1    15  0.5674E+03  0.3089E+02  0.3091E+02  0.3686E+00
REACH 1     0     1    16  0.5674E+03  0.3088E+02  0.3091E+02  0.3686E+00
REACH 1     0     1    17  0.5674E+03  0.3086E+02  0.3090E+02  0.3686E+00
REACH 1     0     1    18  0.5674E+03  0.3084E+02  0.3090E+02  0.3686E+00
REACH 1     0     1    19  0.5674E+03  0.3082E+02  0.3089E+02  0.3686E+00
REACH 1     0     1    20  0.5674E+03  0.3081E+02  0.3088E+02  0.3686E+00
REACH 1     0     1    21  0.5674E+03  0.3079E+02  0.3088E+02  0.3686E+00
REACH 1     0     1    22  0.5674E+03  0.3077E+02  0.3087E+02  0.3686E+00
REACH 1     0     1    23  0.5674E+03  0.3076E+02  0.3086E+02  0.3686E+00
REACH 1     0     1    24  0.5674E+03  0.3074E+02  0.3086E+02  0.3686E+00
REACH 2     0     1     1  0.6911E+02  0.2352E+00  0.2625E+00  0.2460E-02
REACH 2     0     1     2  0.6911E+02  0.2352E+00  0.2589E+00  0.2459E-02
REACH 2     0     1     3  0.6911E+02  0.2352E+00  0.2557E+00  0.2458E-02
REACH 2     0     1     4  0.6911E+02  0.2352E+00  0.2530E+00  0.2457E-02
REACH 2     0     1     5  0.6911E+02  0.2352E+00  0.2505E+00  0.2456E-02
REACH 2     0     1     6  0.6911E+02  0.2352E+00  0.2484E+00  0.2455E-02
REACH 2     0     1     7  0.6911E+02  0.2352E+00  0.2465E+00  0.2454E-02
REACH 2     0     1     8  0.6911E+02  0.2352E+00  0.2448E+00  0.2454E-02
    
```

Figure 33: Snippet of the output.rch file

7.2 Scenario Analysis

The rainfall pattern depicted in Table 16 was used to generate the scenario for Deduru Oya sub-catchment.

Table16: Selected rainfall values for the scenario generation

Day	Time	Rainfall in mm			
		Paragahadeniya	Rambadagalla	Batalagoda	SB Herath
Day 1	t=10:00	1	0	0	0.2
	t=11:00	0	2.6	0.6	1.2
	t=12:00	0.4	0.6	5.8	7.2
	t=13:00	0.2	0	0	0
	t=14:00	0	0	0	0
	t=15:00	4.6	25.2	2.8	3.6
	t=16:00	0.4	0	0.8	11.2
	t=17:00	4.6	0	0	19.2
t=18:00	0	0	3.6	0	

	t=19:00	0	0.2	0	0.4
	t=20:00	0	0	0	0
	t=21:00	0	0	0.2	0
	t=22:00	0	0	0	0
	t=23:00	0	0	0	0
Day 2	t=00:00	0	0	0	0.4
	t=01:00	0	0.8	0	0

As per the time of concentration values given in Table 13, the generated flow related to the above rainfall condition will reach the reservoir at the 6th hour. As per the above table, the water level of the reservoir starts to rise at 17:00 on Day 1. If we assume no rainfall is occurred after that, the results of the model can be given as per the Table 17.

Table 17: The results of scenario analysis

Day	Time	^a Flow of Deduru Oya sub-catchment(m ³ /s)	^b Flow of other sub-catchments (m ³ /s)	^c Total flow to the reservoir (m ³ /s)	^d Height of the radial gate opening (m)
Day 1	t=17:00	4.14	2.76	6.90	0.5
	t=18:00	4.55	3.03	7.58	0.5
	t=19:00	4.61	3.07	7.69	0.5
	t=20:00	4.55	3.03	7.58	0.5
	t=21:00	4.44	2.96	7.41	0.5
	t=22:00	4.34	2.90	7.24	0.5
	t=23:00	4.23	2.82	7.06	0.5
Day 2	t=00:00	4.17	2.78	6.95	0.5
	t=01:00	4.14	2.76	6.90	0.5
	t=02:00	4.10	2.74	6.84	0.4
	t=03:00	4.10	2.73	6.83	0.4
	t=04:00	4.10	2.74	6.84	0.4
	t=05:00	4.13	2.76	6.89	0.5
	t=06:00	4.23	2.82	7.04	0.5
	t=07:00	4.47	2.98	7.46	0.5
	t=08:00	4.81	3.21	8.02	0.5

	t=09:00	5.15	3.43	8.58	0.6
	t=10:00	5.33	3.56	8.89	0.6
	t=11:00	5.56	3.70	9.26	0.6
	t=12:00	5.59	3.73	9.32	0.6

^a – This column represents the output generated by the model

^b – As per the Figure 21, the flow of the other sub-catchments (Maguru Oya and combined flow of Kimbulwana and Hakwatuna Oya) was assumed as 2/3rd of the Deduru Oya sub-catchment's flow

^c – This column represents the total flow of 3rd and 4th columns

^d – The equation 12 was applied when calculating the height of the radial gate opening

$$h_t = \frac{Q_t}{n \times w \times v} \quad \text{Equation 11}$$

Where h_t is the height of the radial gate opening at t^{th} hour, Q_t is the discharge at t^{th} hour, n is the number of radial gates decided to open (Deduru Oya reservoir has 8 radial gates. For this example, the number of radial gates decided to open was thought as 3), w is the width of the each radial gate (8.5m), v is the average velocity of water discharged at radial gates (it was assumed v as 0.6m/s).

If the reservoir is filled to its crest level at $t = 10:00$ of day 1 and the reservoir managers want to discharge water from it, in order to accommodate the new flow which will arrive the reservoir at $t=17:00$, they can decide the opening height that should maintain at each hour as per the example elaborated above.

8 Conclusion

Despite the technological advancements in data collection and processing methods, still for some nations, it is crucial to produce real time valid hydrological estimations owing to the constraints pertaining to hydro-meteorological data. The project 4ONSE has shown possibilities of overcoming this limitation through open technologies-based weather stations deployed at regional scale. The calibration and validation results of the model have discovered the capability of 4ONSE data in decision making in water resources management.

Most of the hydrological models use different methods pertaining to areal averaging of rainfall, in absence of dense coverage for the catchment area. Each of these methods has its own limitation. The methods such as average depth method and Thiessen polygon method does not account for topographic influences. The Isohyetal method have to be calculated for each rainfall event and this method is very tedious and time consuming. Therefore, when installation of high cost sophisticated weather stations becomes unworkable for regional scale catchment and the broken communication network could not further support for getting real-time data, deployment of open source based low cost dense weather station network is the way forward. The 4ONSE weather station network covers the entire Deduru Oya basin with 27 stations. This arrangement facilitates to simulate the runoff in the sub-catchments and sub-basins with the aid of multiple stations or single single station data. However, the findings in this study has revealed, the performance of the model is high with multiple stations data.

The hydrological model presented in this report was developed using an open source hydrological modelling tool known as SWAT. The total open source framework which applied in this study, starting from getting the weather station data upto running the model, will pave the path for linking all of them into a single system for developing an automated system for regional scale tank / reservoir management. Since SWAT is a physically based semi-distributed model, it doesn't demand massive amount of data liken in the distributed models. As it operates as a continuous model, it doesn't need initial discharge to apply into the model at every occasion that the model runs.

The most cumbersome task in any hydrological model is parameterization. SWAT makes this to an easy task by automatically calculating most of the model parameters, based on the landuse, slope and soil type of the basin, during the process of HRU generation. The SWAT-CUP standalone open source program, which was developed only for calibrating and validating SWAT outputs, further facilitates modellers to obtaining more accurate parameter values while also adhering to inherent stochasticity of the model.

The stochastic nature of the model, doesn't allow users of the model to apply single set of parameter values for every rainfall event. Therefore, further studies are required to generate different groups of parameter values for different rainfall intensities. Since the model was developed to operate at hourly timestep, the continuity of data in 4ONSE weather stations is strongly influenced for generating accurate outputs in the model. Missing of data for continuous period in at least single station can cause for producing unreliable outputs.

Finally, the different uncertainities can also reduce the performance of the model. The uncertainities associated with input data such as weather data, DEM, land use and soil can

contributes for increasing the predictive uncertainties in the model. One example for this is error accompanying in Davis rain gauge during heavy rainfall events. This has caused for reducing some peak flows in the model. Another uncertainty is linked to uncertainties in stage-discharge relationship equations. The equations used in the model might not be valid to present context due to the changes in the river cross sections and the human induced errors while development of the equations.

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Appendix A Photos of the 4nse weather stations installed at Deduru Oya basin

Variable name	Definition
WLATITUDE	Latitude of weather station (decimal degrees)
WLONGITUDE	Longitude of weather station (decimal degrees)
WELEV	Elevation of weather station
RAIN_YRS	The number of years of maximum monthly 0.5 rainfall data used to define values for RAIN_HHMX(1) – RAIN_HHMX(12).
TMPMX _(mon)	<p>Mean daily maximum air temperature for month (°C)</p> $\mu mx_{mon} = \frac{\sum_{d=1}^N T_{mx,mon}}{N}$ <p>Where μmx_{mon} is the mean daily maximum temperature for the month, $T_{mx,mon}$ is the daily maximum temperature on record d in month mon (°C). N is the total number of daily maximum temperature records for month mon.</p>
TMPMN _(mon)	<p>Mean daily minimum air temperature for month (°C).</p> $\mu mn_{mon} = \frac{\sum_{d=1}^N T_{mn,mon}}{N}$ <p>Where μmn_{mon} is the mean daily minimum temperature for the month, $T_{mn,mon}$ is the daily minimum temperature on record d in month mon (°C). N is the total number of daily maximum temperature records for month mon.</p>
TMPSTDMX _(mon)	<p>Standard deviation for daily maximum air temperature in month (°C). This parameter quantifies the variability in maximum temperature for each month. The standard deviation is calculated:</p> $\sigma mx_{mon} = \sqrt{\left[\frac{\sum_{d=1}^N (T_{mx,mon} - \mu mx_{mon})^2}{N - 1} \right]}$ <p>Where σmx_{mon} is the standard deviation for daily maximum temperature in month mon (°C), $T_{mx,mon}$ is the daily maximum temperature on record d on month mon (°C), μmx_{mon} is the average daily maximum temperature for the month (°C), and N is the total number of daily maximum temperature records for month mon.</p>

$TMPSTDMN_{(mon)}$	<p>Standard deviation for daily minimum air temperature in month ($^{\circ}C$).</p> $\sigma_{mn_{mon}} = \sqrt{\left[\frac{\sum_{d=1}^N (T_{mn,mon} - \mu_{mn_{mon}})^2}{N - 1} \right]}$ <p>Where $\sigma_{mn_{mon}}$ is the standard deviation for daily minimum temperature in month mon ($^{\circ}C$), $T_{mn,mon}$ is the daily minimum temperature on record d on month mon ($^{\circ}C$), $\mu_{mn_{mon}}$ is the average daily minimum temperature for the month ($^{\circ}C$), and N is the total number of daily minimum temperature records for month mon.</p>
$PCPMM_{(mon)}$	<p>Mean total monthly precipitation (mm H_2O)</p> $\overline{R_{mon}} = \frac{\sum_{d=1}^N R_{day,mon}}{yrs}$ <p>Where $\overline{R_{mon}}$ is the mean monthly precipitation (mm), $R_{day,mon}$ is the daily precipitation for record d in month mon, N is the total number of records in the month mon used to calculate the average, and yrs is the number of years of daily precipitation records used in calculation.</p>
$PCPSTD_{(mon)}$	<p>Standard deviation for daily precipitation in month (mm/day). This parameter quantifies the variability in precipitation for each month. The standard deviation is calculated:</p> $\sigma_{mon} = \sqrt{\left[\frac{\sum_{d=1}^N (R_{day,mon} - \overline{R_{mon}})^2}{N - 1} \right]}$ <p>Where σ_{mon} is the standard deviation for daily precipitation in month mon (mm), $R_{day,mon}$ is the amount of precipitation for record d in month mon (mm), $\overline{R_{mon}}$ is the average precipitation for the month (mm), and N is the total number of daily precipitation records for month mon.</p>
$PCPSKW_{(mon)}$	<p>Skew coefficient for daily precipitation in month. This parameter quantifies the symmetry of the precipitation distribution about the monthly mean. The skew coefficient is calculated:</p> $g_{mon} = \frac{N \cdot \sum_{d=1}^N (R_{day,mon} - \overline{R_{mon}})^3}{(N - 1)(n - 2)(\sigma_{mon}^3)}$ <p>Where g_{mon} is the skew coefficient for precipitation in the month, N is the total number of daily precipitation records for month mon, $R_{day,mon}$ is the amount of precipitation for record d</p>

	<p>in month mon (mm), and σ_{mon} is the standard deviation for daily precipitation in month mon (mm).</p>
PR_W _(1,mon)	<p>Probability of a wet day following a dry day in the month. This probability is calculated:</p> $P_i\left(\frac{W}{D}\right) = \frac{days_{\overline{D},i}}{days_{dry,i}}$ <p>Where $P_i\left(\frac{W}{D}\right)$ is the probability of a wet day following a dry day in month i, $days_{\overline{D},i}$ is the number of times a wet day followed a dry day in month i for the entire period of record, and $days_{dry,i}$ is the number of dry days in month i during the entire period of record. A dry day is a day with 0 mm of precipitation. A wet day is a day with > 0mm precipitation.</p>
PR_W _(2,mon)	<p>Probability of a wet day following a wet day in the month. This probability is calculated:</p> $P_i\left(\frac{W}{W}\right) = \frac{days_{\overline{W},i}}{days_{wet,i}}$ <p>Where $P_i\left(\frac{W}{W}\right)$ is the probability of a wet day following a wet day in month i, $days_{\overline{W},i}$ is the number of times a wet day followed a wet day in month i for the entire period of record, and $days_{wet,i}$ is the number of wet days in month i during the entire period of record. A dry day is a day with 0 mm of precipitation. A wet day is a day with > 0mm precipitation.</p>
PCPD _(mon)	<p>Average number of days of precipitation in month. This parameter is calculated:</p> $\overline{d_{wet,i}} = \frac{days_{wet,i}}{yrs}$ <p>Where $\overline{d_{wet,i}}$ is the average number of days of precipitation in month i, $days_{wet,i}$ is the number of wet days in month i during the entire period of record, and yrs is the number of years of record.</p>
RAINHHMX _(mon)	<p>Maximum 0.5 hour rainfall in entire period of record for month (mm). This value represents the most extreme 30-minute rainfall intensity recorded in the entire period of record.</p>
SOLARAV _(mon)	<p>Average daily solar radiation for month (MJ/m²/day). This value is calculated by summing the total solar radiation for every day</p>

	<p>in the month for all years of record and dividing by the number of days summed:</p> $\mu rad_{mon} = \frac{\sum_{d=1}^N H_{day,mon}}{N}$ <p>Where μrad_{mon} is the mean daily solar radiation for the month (MJ/m²/day), $H_{day,mon}$ is the total solar radiation reaching the earth's surface for day d in month mon (MJ/m²/day), and N is the total number of daily solar radiation records for month mon.</p>
DEWPT _(mon)	<p>Average daily dew point temperature for each month (°C) or relative humidity (fraction) can be input.</p> <p>If all twelve months are less than one, the model assumes relative humidity is input. If any month has a value greater than 1.0, the model assumes dew point temperature is input.</p> <p>Dew point temperature is the temperature at which the actual vapor pressure present in the atmosphere is equal to the saturation vapor pressure. This value is calculated by summing the dew point temperature for every day in the month for all years of record and dividing by the number of days summed:</p> $\mu dew_{mon} = \frac{\sum_{d=1}^N T_{dew,mon}}{N}$ <p>Where μdew_{mon} is the mean daily dew point temperature for the month (°C), $T_{dew,mon}$ is the dew point temperature for day d in month mon (°C), and N is the total number of daily dew point records for month mon.</p>
WND _{AV(mon)}	<p>Average daily wind speed in month (m/s).</p> <p>This value is calculated by summing the average or mean wind speed values for every day in the month for all years of record and dividing by the number of days summed:</p> $\mu wnd_{mon} = \frac{\sum_{d=1}^N \mu_{wnd,mon}}{N}$ <p>Where μwnd_{mon} is the mean daily wind speed for the month (m/s), $\mu_{wnd,mon}$ is the average wind speed for day d in month mon (m/s), and N is the total number of daily wind speed records for month mon.</p>

Appendix B Definitions of the SWAT hydrological parameters

	Parameter	Definition	Units
1	ESCO	Soil evapotranspiration compensation factor	-
2	EPCO	Plant uptake compensation factor	-
3	CANMX	Maximum canopy storage	mm
4	SOL_ALB	Moist soil albedo	-
5	GW_REVAP	Groundwater "revap" coefficient	-
6	REVAPMN	Threshold depth of water in the shallow aquifer for percolation to the deep aquifer to occur	mm
7	CNCOEF	Plant evapotranspiration curve number coefficient	-
8	SURLAG	Surface runoff lag coefficient	-
9	CN2	Initial SCS runoff curve number for moisture condition II	-
10	CH_L(1)	Longest tributary channel length in subbasin	km
11	CH_S(1)	Average slope of tributary channels	m/m
12	CH_N(1)	Manning's "n" value for the tributary channels	-
13	CH_W(1)	Average width of tributary channels	m
14	CH_K(1)	Effective hydraulic conductivity in tributary channel alluvium	mm/hr
15	SLSUBBSN	Average slope length	m
16	OV_N	Manning's "n" value for overland flow	-
17	SOL_CRK	Potential or maximum crack volume of the soil profile expressed as a fraction of the total soil volume	fraction
18	FFCB	Initial soil water storage	-
19	SOL_Z	Depth from soil surface to bottom of layer	mm
20	SOL_BD	Moist bulk density	Mg/m ³ or g/cm ³
21	SOL_AWC	Available water capacity of the soil layer	mm
22	SOL_K	Saturated hydraulic conductivity	mm/hr

23	HRU_SLP	Average slope steepness	m/m
24	LAT_TTIME	Lateral flow travel time	days
25	SLSOIL	Slope length for lateral subsurface flow	m
26	SHALLST	Initial depth of water in the shallow aquifer	mm
27	DEEPST	Initial depth of water in the deep aquifer	mm
28	GW_DELAY	Ground water delay time	days
29	ALPHA_BF	Baseflow alpha factor	1/days
30	GWQMN	Threshold depth of water in the shallow aquifer required for return flow to occur	mm
31	GW_REVAP	Groundwater "revap" coefficient	-
32	REVAPMN	Threshold depth of water in the shallow aquifer for "revap" or percolation to the deep aquifer to occur	mm
33	RCHRG_DP	Deep aquifer percolation factor	-
34	WUSHAL	Average daily water removal from the shallow aquifer for the month	10 ⁴ m ³ /day
35	WUDEEP	Average daily water removal from the deep aquifer for the month	10 ⁴ m ³ /day
36	TRNSRCH	Fraction of transmission losses from main channel that enter deep aquifer	-
37	EVRCH	Reach evaporation adjustment factor	-
38	MSK_CO1	Muskingum coefficient for normal flow	-
39	MSK_CO2	Muskingum coefficient for low flow	-
40	MSK_X	Weighting factor for wedge storage	-
41	CH_W(2)	Average width of main channel at top of bank	m
42	CH_D	Depth of main channel from top of bank to bottom	m
43	CH_S(2)	Average slope of main channel along the channel length	m/m
44	CH_L(2)	Length of main channel	km
45	CH_N(2)	Manning's "n" value for main channel	-
46	CH_K(2)	Effective hydraulic conductivity in main channel alluvium	mm/hr
47	ALPHA_BNK	Baseflow alpha factor for bank storage	days

Appendix C Number of the day in the year

Day	January	February	March*	April*	May*	June*	July*	August*	September*	October*	November*	December*
1	1	32	60	91	121	152	182	213	244	274	305	335
2	2	33	61	92	122	153	183	214	245	275	306	336
3	3	34	62	93	123	154	184	215	246	276	307	337
4	4	35	63	94	124	155	185	216	247	277	308	338
5	5	36	64	95	125	156	186	217	248	278	309	339
6	6	37	65	96	126	157	187	218	249	279	310	340
7	7	38	66	97	127	158	188	219	250	280	311	341
8	8	39	67	98	128	159	189	220	251	281	312	342
9	9	40	68	99	129	160	190	221	252	282	313	343
10	10	41	69	100	130	161	191	222	253	283	314	344
11	11	42	70	101	131	162	192	223	254	284	315	345
12	12	43	71	102	132	163	193	224	255	285	316	346
13	13	44	72	103	133	164	194	225	256	286	317	347
14	14	45	73	104	134	165	195	226	257	287	318	348
15	15	46	74	105	135	166	196	227	258	288	319	349
16	16	47	75	106	136	167	197	228	259	289	320	350
17	17	48	76	107	137	168	198	229	260	290	321	351
18	18	49	77	108	138	169	199	230	261	291	322	352
19	19	50	78	109	139	170	200	231	262	292	323	353
20	20	51	79	110	140	171	201	232	263	293	324	354
21	21	52	80	111	141	172	202	233	264	294	325	355
22	22	53	81	112	142	173	203	234	265	295	326	356
23	23	54	82	113	143	174	204	235	266	296	327	357
24	24	55	83	114	144	175	205	236	267	297	328	358
25	25	56	84	115	145	176	206	237	268	298	329	359
26	26	57	85	116	146	177	207	238	269	299	330	360
27	27	58	86	117	147	178	208	239	270	300	331	361
28	28	59	87	118	148	179	209	240	271	301	332	362
29	29	(60)	88	119	149	180	210	241	272	302	333	363
30	30	-	89	120	150	181	211	242	273	303	334	364
31	31	-	90	-	151	-	212	243	-	304	-	365

* add 1 if leap year